

ISic0779

I.Sicily inscription 0779

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco

Object

painted wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of Vigna Cassia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di Vigna Cassia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἰθαλλας ναύκληρος Λεππημαγν ἐν(σιος) ἐτῶν λε

Apparatus

Text of 1985

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644898

PHI 329588

PHI 329589

PHI 331126

Bibliography

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